

Analysing Drivers Affecting Attitude Towards Fintech Adoption -A Structural Equation Modelling Approach

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this research is to study the drivers affecting banking consumers' insights towards the adoption of FinTech services provided by banks.

Research Methodology – Data for the study was collected through a structured questionnaire which received 212 responses, for the analysis and hypothesis testing Structural Equation Modelling approach has been used.

Findings – This study demonstrates that using banking Fintech services is positively impacted by financial attitude and behaviour. The findings imply that favourable circumstances will arise from users having sound financial behaviour and attitudes because this will increase respondents' attitudes toward utilising FinTech services

Practical implications – The results suggest that the government should focus on financial literacy, which will raise the level of financial behaviour and attitude resulting in an upsurge in the adoption of digital banking services.

Originality/Value – This study is an attempt to identify the drivers resulting in a positive association towards the adoption of FinTech services provided by banks.

Keywords (3–5): FinTech, Financial Behaviour, Financial Attitude, E-Banking, Mobile Wallets

Introduction

The technologically advanced cutting-edge and digital platforms that assist consumers or banks in providing banking services in better, faster ways are referred to as "FinTech" in our terminology. Although the financial sector has undergone numerous digital transitions, new goods and services have also been produced as a result. (Huston, 2010) claims that there are two aspects to financial literacy: awareness, which stands for the individual's own financial education, and use, which relates to the administration of that information.

(Z. Chen et al., 2017) The banking sector has seen a tremendous transformation as a result of the advancement of financial technology, which includes sectors like mobile Internet, cloud computing, big data, search engines, and blockchains. (Jünger & Mietzner, 2020) Peer-to-peer lending, crowdfunding, mobile payment systems, AI, machine learning, and even a variety of digital currencies like cryptocurrencies and NFTs, have all emerged over the past ten years.

(Z. Chen et al., 2017) Since the advent of the Internet, the banking sector has increasingly networked, which has accelerated the integrated data development of banking institutions. People are moving toward digital adaptation at a higher rate in Asian regions where smartphone ownership is more prevalent than in other markets. Asia-Pacific regions witnessed an upsurge in the usage of services powered by Fin-tech. (EY Global, 2022) Except for India, which is almost equal to Asia's leading digital power China, most countries still trail China's 87%

penetration by a significant margin. (Lagna & Ravishankar, 2022) Fintech advances offer to open up access to financial services including payments, savings, credit, and insurance for the underprivileged. (Z. Chen et al., 2017) The combination of mobile Internet adaption and the principles of financial contracts fosters the continuous improvement of financial systems.

The growth of the banking industry is fuelled by advancements in financial technology. (Li & Xu, 2021) FinTech makes it easier and more affordable for more people, particularly the poor, to access financial services, while also sharing more reform outcomes. (Chen et al., 2019) FinTech has gained popularity, and many analysts consider FinTech has the ability to drastically change financial services by making transactions more affordable, convenient, and secure. (Agarwal & Zhang, 2020) Because of this, Digital wallets are more practical and user-friendly than traditional methods. Unlike debit and credit cards, digital wallets don't need a POS machine or any bank account information to be disclosed.

Recent development in the form of UPI enables customers to pay by scanning the QR codes or through virtual payment address or through different applications such as Paytm, PhonePe, BHIM etc to pay them in e-wallets virtually 24*7 with the help of smartphones. (Agarwal & Zhang, 2020) With the quick popularity of mobile devices and mobile internet over the past several years, both developed and developing countries have witnessed considerable improvements in digitalisation. (Hamid et al., 2016) People are more likely to become familiar with a system's features and eventually intend to keep using it if it is relatively simple to use. (Pathirana & Azam, 2018) Therefore, if the FinTech platform is more adaptable, it will lessen the requirement for a consumer to adjust their lifestyle. In recent years, a number of financial institutions have gone digital, Government of India and NPCI working towards the promotion of FinTech services in India with introduction of UPI, E-rupee, Positive Pay System (PPS) and tokenisation in debit and credit card payments. The motive behind this is to promote the FinTech adoptability among the banking consumers

Review Of Literature & Hypothesis Formation

Financial Behaviour

The term "financial Behavior" refers to human behaviour that is associated with managing money. (Anand et al., 2021) A person's fundamental knowledge of banking services and products, numeracy skills and methods for managing income are addressed as financial behaviour. (Saurabh & Nandan, 2018) noted that "financial behaviour" refers to how one manages their income and financial condition, or how they are inclined to handle day-to-day financial issues. (Potrich et al., 2016) It has been acknowledged as vital for those who work in a highly complicated environment. Financial analysts have historically preferred (Bongomin et al., 2018) to create financial behaviour materials under the presumption that if people are given knowledge and financial tools, they will be better able to choose the options to reach their financial objectives. Thus, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

H1: Financial behaviour is significantly associated with the attitude towards FinTech services adoption.

Financial Attitude

(Winarta & Pamungkas, 2020) When assessing financial management practises, a person's opinion and judgement are expressed as a state of mind or psychological inclination known as their financial attitude. (Anthony et al., 2011) Financial attitude is the use of financial principles in decision-making and effective resource allocation to create and preserve value. (Potrich, Vieira, & Silva, 2016) With the exception of the expectation regarding the association between knowledge and attitude, a study's findings support the notion that financial attitudes and knowledge have a favourable impact on financial conduct if someone has a good financial attitude, their digital attitude will improve. Thus, the following hypothesis has been formulated: **H2:** Financial Attitude is significantly associated with the attitude towards FinTech services adoption.

Facilitating Conditions

(Chawla & Joshi, 2021) The availability, usability, and affordability of technological resources are referred to as "facilitating conditions" that help in the adoption of new technology. These can include factors like the cost of smartphones and internet tariff, availability of internet services, knowledge and familiarity with technology etc. From the viewpoint of FinTech services, it is feasible to anticipate that good FC would result in a strong inclination towards its adoption. According to (Jünger & Mietzner, 2020) household's inclination to migrate to FinTech is influenced by its level of confidence and familiarity with new technologies, financial literacy, and general transparency.

H3: Facilitating Conditions are significantly associated with the attitude towards FinTech services adoption.

Figure 1 - Proposed Conceptual Model

Research Methodology

Data for the study was collected through a structured questionnaire. The convenience sampling method was used to select the study's respondents and received 212 responses. Based on a review of the literature on FinTech services and mobile wallets, this study proposes a conceptual framework that considers financial behaviour, facilitating conditions, financial attitude, and their association with attitudes toward FinTech adoption. Three exogenous variables namely financial attitude (FA), financial behaviour (FB), and Facilitating Conditions

(FC) and one endogenous variable Attitude (AT) compose the model (see Figure 1). AT is a dependent variable and FA, FB & FC are the independent variables. To measure AT scale developed by (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2003), for measuring FA scale developed by (Nano & Istrofor, 2017; Potrich et al., 2016), for FB scale developed by (Kumar et al., 2017; Nano & Istrofor, 2017; Potrich et al., 2016) and to measure FC scale developed by (Shaw, 2015; Shuhaiber, 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2003) has been used. The questionnaire consisted of 17 questions on a 5-point Likert scale to measure the respondent's behaviour with 5 as strongly agree and 1 as strongly disagree.

Demographic Profile Of Respondents

Table 1 – Demographic profile of Respondents

Demographic Factors		N	%
Gender	Male	65	69.34
	Female	147	30.66
Age Group	16 – 23 Years	20	9.45
	24 – 32 Years	86	40.56
	33 – 40 Years	61	28.77
	Above 40 Years	45	21.22
Level of Education	Intermediate	15	7.07
	Graduate	67	31.60
	Post Graduate	91	42.93
	M.Phil & Ph.D.	39	18.40
Income Level	Upto Rs.20000	24	11.32
	Rs. 20000 – 40000	115	54.25
	Rs. 40000 – 60000	48	22.64
	Above Rs. 60000	25	11.79

Source: The Authors

By reconnecting the association between respondents' financial behavioural traits, attitude, facilitating conditions and their attitude, this study examines the adoption of FinTech services like mobile wallets, net banking, UPI, and other e-banking services offered by various banking institutions. In Table 1, demographic characteristics shown of the 212 respondents. The statistical results indicate that, out of the 212 respondents, 69.34% were female and 30.66% were male. The highest percentage of respondents (40.56%) were in the age range of 24 - 32 years, followed by 28.77% in the 33 - 40 age group, 21.22% in the group of people over 40 years old, and 9.45% in the 16 - 23 age group. (Hossain et al., 2019) that mobile phones are one of the essential reasons for re-establishing contact between businesses and consumers, our study results are supported by (Hossain et al., 2019) results in terms of smartphone usage in a

day, 48.55% of respondents reported that they spend more than 4 hours a day on average on the smartphone.

Data Analysis & Results

(Hossain et al., 2020) KMO measurements are used to establish the sampling efficiency that was used to assess if the responses acquired from the sample were sufficient or not. Table 2 represents the KMO value of 0.813, (Cerny & Kaiser, 1977) values greater than 0.8 can be considered good, i.e., an indication that component or factor analysis will be useful for these variables.

Table 2 - KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.813
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1917.047
	Df	136
	Sig.	.000

Source: The Authors

(Ruvio et al., 2008) The average extracted variance, which serves as a measure of convergent validity, represents the degree of correlation of various indicators for a variable (Chin, 1998) of the latent variable, the CR, and the loading of corresponding measurable variables. Table 3 shows that the values of composite reliability (CR) of each multi-item measure are > 0.70, (Hossain et al., 2020) which represents high internal consistency among items also the value of AVE is > 0.50 which provides support for convergent validity. (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) recommended that Cronbach's alpha be greater than 0.8. and in our study for all constructs, it has been found more than .8 which reflects the high reliability of the measuring instrument.

Table 3 – Summary of Exploratory Factor Analysis

Variables	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE	MSV
FB1	.928				
FB2	.941				
FB3	.927	.889	0.882	0.652	0.022
FB4	.881				
FB5	.851				
FA1	.764				
FA2	.836	.867	0.869	0.628	0.042
FA3	.897				

FA4	.775				
FC1	.674				
FC2	.930	.866	0.868	0.623	0.024
FC3	.899				
FC4	.838				
AT1	.838				
AT2	.817	.864	0.867	0.623	0.042
AT3	.846				
AT4	.740				

Source: The Authors

By estimating a confirmatory factor analysis model with AMOS and measuring the relationship between the independent and dependent variables using path analysis, it was possible to assess the validity and reliability of the constructs. The validity and reliability of the factor-based test, which is represented in Table 3, were successfully tested.

Figure 2 - CFA Model

Source – The Authors

Model Fit

Table 3 shows the model fit data analysed through AMOS. (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010) A good fitting model is accepted if the value of CMIN/DF is < 5, the goodness-of-fit (GFI) indices, (Tucker & Lewis, 1973) the Tucker and Lewis (TLI) index is >.90, & (McDonald & Ho, 2002) the Confirmatory fit index (CFI) >.95. (Klem, 2000; McDonald & Ho, 2002) In addition, an adequate filling model accepted if the AMOS computed value of standardized root mean square residual (RMR) and root mean square error approximation is < 0.05. Table 3 shows the fit indices of structured model as all values fall in the acceptable range: CMIN/DF = 1.234, CFI = .986, GFI = .915, AGFI = .905, TLI = .983, RMSEA = .033 & RMR = 0.022. As all values lies in the acceptable range in the structured model represent a better fit of the data.

Table 4 – Goodness Fit of CFA Model

Model	CMIN/DF	CFI	GFI	AGFI	TLI	RMSEA	RMR
CFA	1.234	.986	.930	.905	.983	0.033	0.022

Source: The Authors

Figure 3 - Structural Model

Source – The Authors

Path Analysis Results

This study assessed the association between FA, FB, and FC on AT towards FinTech adoption. As per the result of path analysis financial behaviour is significantly associated with the attitude towards banking FinTech services as $b = .204$, $t = 3.190$ and P value = .001. Also, financial attitude is significantly associated with the attitude towards FinTech services as $b = .131$, $t = 2.246$ and P value = .025. But, facilitating conditions are not significantly associated with the attitude towards banking FinTech services as $b = .077$, $t = 1.214$ and P value = .225. Thus, the findings in Table 5 support H1 & H2 but H3 was rejected as the P value is > 0.05 of H3.

Table 5 – Result of Structural Model

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
FB → AT	.204	.064	3.190	.001	Supported
FA → AT	.131	.058	2.246	.025	Supported
FC → AT	.077	.063	1.214	.225	Rejected

Source: The Authors

Conclusion

This study discusses the uptake and application of banking FinTech services. This study discovers that financial behaviour and financial attitude have favourable effects on the adoption of banking Fintech services. Results suggest that having sound financial behaviour and attitudes among users will function as a favourable circumstance because it will improve respondents' attitudes toward the adoption of FinTech services, which will increase their likelihood of doing so. In line with the findings of (Chawla & Joshi, 2021) this study also finds that facilitating conditions do not have any significant influences on attitudes towards the adoption of FinTech services. Banking institutions can encourage the use of FinTech services and expand their customer base by influencing consumers' financial attitudes and behaviours. Since consumers can easily manage their bank accounts, make online transfers of money, and pay for a variety of services 24 hours a day using their smartphones with the help of different banking technologies like net banking, e-wallets, and UPI, raising awareness for the adoption of these technologies has become crucial in today's society.

Appendix – 1 (Questionnaire)

S.No	Scale Items		Label	Source
1.	I keep track of my monthly expenses.	Financial Behaviour	FB1	(Kumar et al., 2017; Nano & Istrofor, 2017; Potrich et al., 2016)
2.	I maintain a sufficient balance in my bank account.		FB2	
3.	I worry about how best to manage my money.		FB3	
4.	I compare prices when buying something.		FB4	
5.	I always pay my bills on time to avoid extra charges.		FB5	
1.	My mobile device is appropriate for using a FinTech services.	Facilitating Conditions	FC1	(Shaw, 2015; Shuhaiber, 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2003)
2.	I have the knowledge necessary to use FinTech services.		FC2	
3.	I can easily find a person who can help me out if I get stuck while using FinTech services.		FC3	
4.	I am familiar with FinTech services.		FC4	

1.	It is important to establish financial targets for the future	Financial Attitude	FA1	(Nano & Istrofor, 2017; Potrich et al., 2016)
2.	It is important to have and follow a monthly expense plan.		FA2	
3.	It is important to stay within a budget.		FA3	
4.	I think it is very important to set aside each month sum of money in order to invest or deposit.		FA4	
1.	I feel using Fintech services nowadays is a good idea.	Attitude	AT1	(Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2003)
2.	I like the concept of using Fintech services offered by banks.		AT2	
3.	I think using Fintech services is enjoyable		AT3	
4.	I value the benefits of Fintech Services.		AT4	

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